

DEVELOPMENT OF AN EXTERNALLY PRESSURIZED HYDROSTATIC
RING TEST METHOD FOR THE MECHANICAL
CHARACTERIZATION OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The development of a test fixture which produces hydrostatic external pressure on a thick-walled ring is described. Pressures up to a maximum of 138 MPa (20 kpsi) have been achieved. Tests which verify that the fixture creates the desired pressure boundary condition were performed; analytical predictions and experimental results were in agreement. This test fixture permits in-test measurement using strain gages, photoelastic coatings, acoustic emission, high speed photography and moire interferometry. Results of tests using this fixture for rings taken from cylinders having different graphite fiber/polymer matrix material systems are presented. Failure pressure was highly dependent on the presence of localized wavy circumferential plies created during curing. The effect of wavy plies on the strain distribution in the ring cross-section is clearly demonstrated using moire interferometry.

KEY WORDS: Hydrostatic test; ring test; testing of composite material; wavy plies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The advantages of using composite materials for submersible applications are due to their high specific buoyancy, strength, and stiffness. The mechanical behavior of thick-walled composite cylinder under external hydrostatic compressive loading has been the subject of on going research in the last ten years. The issues of manufacturing processes, analytical modeling and testing have been the major topics of research interest. The characterization of such structures and the evaluation of their performance have been relying heavily on testing complete cylinders. Testing cylinders is an expensive and time consuming task, and does not provide enough information to understand how such thick

composite cylindrical structures behave under external pressure with respect to through the thickness kinematics. Often, the test results are clouded with end-closure effect that have been reported to be a separate problem, different from the cylinder membrane behavior [1, 3]. Testing ring specimens is an effective method for research investigation. Composite ring specimens produce approximately the same radial and hoop stresses as in the cylinder membrane [4]. Few test methods have been developed to test ring specimens [1 - 5]. These test methods load the ring in a displacement constrained mode. Such methods do not reflect the actual loading condition as in submersible environment which is a pressure type loading condition. Also, available test methods do not provide the versatility as a research tool to incorporate the benefit of using modern experimental mechanics methods to fully understand composite material behavior under external compressive pressure.

Recent work by Garala [2 and 3] in testing thick-walled graphite/epoxy cylinders, loaded by external pressure, indicates large differences between predictions based on strength of flat laminates and test results. Such large differences raise questions about realizing optimum utilization of composite material in this application. Hyer et al. [6] proposed that the decrease in strength is caused by increased stresses in regions of waviness of plies created in thick sections during manufacturing. Hyer [4] showed that a ring taken from a cylinder with 2:1 hoop/axial fiber distribution shows nearly the same circumferential and radial stress distribution as the cylinder, with the extensional radial strain less uniformly distributed through the wall. Because there is no axial stress in the ring, the axial strain in the ring is different than in the cylinder. In all likelihood, failure is influenced primarily by circumferential and radial loading; thus, the ring appears to be a suitable alternative test specimen. The ring test permits direct observation and measurement of radial and circumferential deformations using strain gages, photoelastic coatings and moire interferometry. Consequently the importance of manufacturing anomalies such as wavy plies may be assessed. In addition, nonlinearities not considered by Hyer et al. [6] may be monitored. The following sections describe the test fixture, test procedures, and significant results from numerous tests that have been conducted using this fixture.

2. TEST FIXTURE AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The test fixture, Figure 1, consists of two hardened steel plates, one called the cavity plate and the other called the cover plate. The cavity plated contains a cylindrical cavity that houses a toroidal shaped urethane rubber bladder having a square cross-section which fits into the cavity with zero clearance. The hardness of the bladder was Shore D-70. Two integral stainless steel stems permit entry or exit of hydraulic fluid. These stems pass through the center of T-shaped hardened steel inserts which fit closely in T-shaped slots in the face of the cavity plate and extend outside the periphery of the cavity. The high pressure source is connected to one of the stems and a valve used to bleed air from the bladder is connected to the other stem. Inside the bladder is fit a urethane rubber anti-extrusion band which conforms closely over the outer periphery of the test ring. The rubber band has the same width as the test ring which is slightly less than the depth of the cavity (typically 0.15 mm which allows for increase in the width of the ring that occurs during the test due to Poisson expansion). The hardness of the band was Shore D-90. The clearance between the ring width and the depth of the cavity is critical. If the clearance is too great, the band and the bladder will extrude through the clearance between the interior surfaces of the cover plate and the faces of

the ring and if the clearance is too small, Poisson expansion will cause interference between the ring faces and the adjacent plate surfaces. The band, so placed between the bladder and the test ring, protects the bladder from extrusion and potential damage when the test ring fails. Finally, the cover plate is secured to the cavity plate by twenty-two 3/4-inch high-strength steel bolts which are heavily preloaded so that the band and bladder do not extrude from the small clearance between the plates and the ring. Provisions are made in the cavity plate for passage strain gage lead wires and acoustic emission monitoring cables. There are three versions of the cover plate: one for testing rings to failure without visual observation, a second which allows monitoring approximately 90 percent of the ring cross-section using a photoelastic coating or high-speed photography and a third which permits measuring displacements in the ring cross-section using moiré interferometry. Abdallah et al. [7] present a detailed description of the tests which verify that the fixture provides the desired pressure boundary condition.

FIGURE 1. Test Fixture

Rings having a 17.78 cm (7.00 in.) inside diameter and nominal 1.58 cm (0.62 in.) wall-thickness were cut from cylinders using standard machining practices for graphite-epoxy material. Only the width of the rings was determined by machining; the as-manufactured inner and outer surfaces of the rings were not machined. The thickness of the rings was 2.54 (+0.00/0.007 cm) (1.00 (+0.000/-0.003 in.)). All tests utilized a minimum of four biaxial strain rosettes placed at 90 degree intervals on the inner surface of the ring. Many tests also used three polyvinylidene fluoride sensors placed at 120 degree intervals on the inner surface which monitored acoustic emission during pressurization. These signals indicated the location of failure initiation, and were used

to start a high-speed film recording camera operating at 2000 frames/sec. At this speed resolution of failure between consecutive frames was not possible indicating that the final failure event occurs in less than 0.5 msec. Photoelastic coatings were used to observe the strain distribution differences between rings of high manufacturing quality and those containing wavy layers and other anomalies. A special normal incidence polariscope using a high-intensity pulsed light source was used to record the color isochromatics as the rings were pressurized. Perturbations in the strain distribution were observed in the regions of layer waviness. These observations motivated the use of moire interferometry to measure the displacements in these wavy regions. Cross-line diffraction gratings of 1200 lines/mm were replicated in typical wavy regions with the grating lines aligned with the radial and circumferential directions. The procedures used followed closely those described by Post [8]. In order to demonstrate the versatility of moire interferometry in this application, experiments were performed using an isotropic ring (6061-T651 aluminum) in which the orthogonal displacement fields in the cross-section were determined at intervals of 2.45 MPa up to 24.13 MPa (0.5 kpsi to 3.5 kpsi). Comparison with the elasticity solution (Gascoigne and Abdallah[9]) shows excellent agreement. The high sensitivity and spatial resolution of moire interferometry make it the only measurement method capable of determining the displacements (and corresponding strains) on the ply level.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of testing numerous composite rings to failure are presented in Table 1. Rings of high manufacturing quality delivered high failure pressures at a measured maximum hoop strain at the inside diameter of 1.4 percent. Figure 2 shows a typical failed ring and Figure 3 gives the corresponding circumferential (hoop) strain versus pressure response determined from a layer-by-layer elasticity solution. The measured response is nonlinear (softening). A similar mode of failure was found for all of the rings given in Table 1. An oblique plane of failure was observed at an angle of approximately 40 degrees from a tangent to the outside diameter and running parallel to the ring axis for all the rings, regardless of fiber/matrix materials or manufacturing methods. This mode of failure suggests that shear plays a major role in the failure process.

FIGURE 2.
Typical Ring
Failure

TABLE 1. TEST RESULTS FOR EXTERNALLY PRESSURIZED RINGS

Ring No.	Material Systems & Layup	Process	Failure Pressure
5184-2A	AS4/DEREKANE	SC-FW	12.80 (8.90)# kpsi(a)
5184-2B	{ $[\pm 84.5_3 / (+ 13.3 / -11.6)_2]_{22} / \pm 84.5_4$ } ^(b)		12.16
5184-3A	AS4/55A	SC-FW	15.45(8.95)##
5184-3F	{ $[\pm 84.5_3 / (+ 13.3 / -11.6)_2]_{22} / \pm 84.5_4$ }		13.76
5184-4A			15.88 (12.44)##
5184-4B			16.59
5184-4C	AS4/3501-6	2MC-FW	10.00-NTF
5184-4D*	{ $[\pm 84.5_3 / (+ 13.3 / -11.6)_2]_{22} / \pm 84.5_4$ }		17.30
5184-4E			14.67
5184-4F			5.00-NTF
5184-6A	IM6/3501-6	2MC-FW	10.45 (9.47)#
5184-6B	{ $[\pm 84.5_3 / (+ 13.3 / -11.6)_2]_{22} / \pm 84.5_4$ }		10.95
5184-6C			11.68
89-1A	AS4/3501-6	3MC-FP	17.00
89-1,934A1	[90 ₃ /0] ₂₀ /90 ₃		16.68-NTF
89-1R6R1			9.04-NTF
MAC1A	AS4/PEEK, 90°	Thermo-plastic	7.23 (0.89 cm wall)
89-2C			8.38-FTT 5.82
90-2D			10.93
89-2E			8.62
89-2F			9.46
89-2G	AS4/3501-6	SC-FP	9.89
89-2H**	[90 ₃ /0] ₂₀ /90 ₃		6.92-FTT 8.44
89-2I**			8.43-FTT 8.36
89-2J**			9.43
89-2K**			10.28
89-2L			8.00-NTF

(a) Values in MPa determined by multiplying values in kpsi by 6.89.

(b) Fiber Orientation angles are measured in degrees from the axis of the cylinder

LEGEND:

SC	= Single Cure	FP	= Fiber Placement	FTT	= First Test To
FW	= Filament Wound	*	= 1,000 psi/min.	#	= Same Cylinder-Ref. 1
MC	= Multi-compaction	**	= 10,000 psi/min.	##	= Similar Cylinder-Ref.1
2 or 3	= Curing Stages	NTF	= Not to Failure		

FIGURE 3. Pressure-Strain Response

Figure 4 shows the displacement fringes (U and V) in a symmetrical wavy region of ring 89-2L. U and V correspond to the radial and circumferential directions in the area of a strip narrow in the y-direction. The angular extent of the interference fringes is 12 degrees. The amplitude and wave-length of the wavy plies can be easily determined from these figures. In this area of the ring, the wave amplitude increases gradually from the inner to the outer diameter. Normal and shearing strains are determined from the derivatives of the displacements: $\epsilon_x = \partial U / \partial x$, $\epsilon_y = \partial V / \partial y$, $\gamma_{xy} = \partial U / \partial y + \partial V / \partial x$. At the inflection points of the waves, $\partial U / \partial y$ is large while $\partial V / \partial x$ is negligible. Hence, a large shear strain develops at these points, increasing with increasing wave amplitude. The hoop strain, ϵ_y , is also larger at the inflection points than at other locations on the wave profile. This combination of high shearing and normal strain at the inflection points may cause failure initiation. Influence of the effect of wave anomalies on failure strength is suggested by the comparison of the results of the 5184 Series and the 89-2 Series rings. The layer waviness in the 5184 Series was very slight and more random than the pronounced in-phase wave "packets" exhibited in the 89-2 Series. Since the material distribution was approximately the same for these series (65% hoop, 35% axial fiber), the large difference of failure pressure is most likely due to the presence of the pronounced wavy plies in the 89-2 Series rings.

FIGURE 4. U and V Displacement Fields for Ring 89-2L at 27.5 MPa (4 kpsi) external pressure.
 Note: added black area to simulate outer radius.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A simple and effective test method for external pressurization of rings has been developed. Verification of the true hydrostatic pressure provided by a newly designed test fixture has been accomplished using metal rings. The application of this new fixture in testing rings taken from graphite composite cylinders proceeded without extreme difficulty. Implementation of various measurement methods was demonstrated on numerous metal and composite rings including strain gages, acoustic emission, high speed video and high speed photography, photoelastic coatings, and moiré interferometry. Conclusions from this study are:

- 1) Manufacturing anomalies are of great importance in contributing to the decrease in failure strength of laminated graphite fiber composite rings loaded by external hydrostatic pressure. High manufacturing quality rings of the present study failed at hoop inner surface strains approaching 1.4% compared with 0.7% (or less) for rings containing wavy plies. Failure in rings containing wavy plies was dominated by local behavior which, prevented achieving the expected ultimate failure strain, strength, and pressure.

- 2) Acoustic emission monitoring proved to be a valuable tool to indicate the progression of damage during testing and to identify the location of catastrophic failure. Triggering of high-speed film or video recording devices immediately prior to failure is facilitated using significant acoustic emission events.
- 3) High-speed video (200 frames/sec.) and film recording (2000 frames/sec.) used in this study were unsuccessful in defining the final failure process, catastrophic failure occurs in less than 0.5 m sec.
- 4) Photoelastic coatings provided high quality images of isochromatic strain fringes occurring in the cross-section of rings, clearly showing the effects of manufacturing anomalies such as localized regions containing wavy plies.
- 5) Moire interferometry provides the ideal method of measurement of the influence of wavy plies on the kinematics of deformation in the cross-section of externally pressurized rings. Careful analysis of the moire patterns, along with examination of failed rings indicated that interlaminar shear is a major controlling factor of catastrophic failure.

5. REFERENCES

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6. BIOGRAPHY

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